

Optimisation of Irradiation Schemes for Radioisotope Production in the MARIA Reactor

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a theoretical and numerical investigation of optimal radioisotope production in the MARIA reactor. A simplified analytical activation model is formulated to describe isotope buildup over repeated irradiation–cooling cycles, yielding closed-form expressions for production efficiency and its cost dependence. The analysis shows that reusing the same targets across cycles consistently improves efficiency, and that multi-cycle irradiation remains economically favourable under realistic MARIA operating conditions. To complement the analytical study, a numerical optimisation framework based on a Genetic Algorithm coupled with Fispect-II activation calculations and Serpent2 flux data was developed. The GA explores irradiation layouts and multi-cycle strategies, and its solutions corroborate the theoretical predictions: optimal schemes systematically retain the same samples across cycles, arranging them in an optimal way. Together, the analytical model and GA-based optimisation provide a compact foundation for evaluating and improving irradiation strategies in research reactors.

Keywords: Radioisotope production, MARIA reactor, Mo-99 production, Metaheuristic optimisation, Cost optimisation

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. MARIA reactor

The MARIA reactor is a 30 MW open-pool research reactor operated by the Polish *National Centre for Nuclear Research* (NCBJ) in Otwock/Świerk. Its core is built around a beryllium moderator matrix that contains pressurized fuel channels, irradiation positions, and control systems (example configuration in Figure 1). Graphite blocks surrounding the matrix act as a reflector, and the entire structure is housed in a conical basket submerged in the reactor pool. The reactor supports multiple irradiation conditions, reaching neutron fluxes of up to 3×10^{14} n/cm²s (thermal) and 2×10^{14} n/cm²s (fast). Vertical channels in the core and reflector region form the main infrastructure for radionuclide production. A major application is the irradiation of TeO₂ targets—around 2000 containers (~200 kg) are processed annually, producing over 1 PBq of I-131. Other routinely produced isotopes include S-35, P-32, Sm-153, Yb-169, and Co-60. The MARIA reactor can produce a wide range of radionuclides essential for manufacturing radiopharmaceuticals and supporting applications in medicine, industry, agriculture, and research [1].

1.2. Mo-99 production and potential optimisation

Among reactor-produced radionuclides, ⁹⁹Mo is particularly important as the parent nuclide of ^{99m}Tc, the dominant isotope in diagnostic imaging. Following global supply issues in 2010 [2], MARIA began irradiating newly developed LEU targets and became a reliable commercial source of ⁹⁹Mo [2, 3].

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Figure 1. Serpent2 model of the beryllium matrix of the MARIA reactor core (an example configuration)

Figure 2. Relative cost of irradiation (Eq. 4) for n cycles, with different ratios of cycle to sample costs ξ .

Despite multiple production sites, shortages persist due to outages and ageing infrastructure, underscoring the need to optimise irradiation processes and strengthen supply security.

Mo-99 is mainly produced through U-235 fission in enriched uranium targets placed in the reactor's neutron field. The reaction rate, $RR = N \cdot \phi \cdot \sigma$, depends on the U-235 atomic density (N), the local neutron flux (ϕ), and the fission cross-section (σ). While n is fixed by target preparation, both ϕ and σ vary significantly across the core. Flux differences can span orders of magnitude, and the fission cross-section changes with neutron energy due to its v^{-1} dependence at low energies and resonance behaviour in the epithermal region. Although the Mo-99 yield per fission is roughly constant at about 6% [4], actual production varies strongly with target location and irradiation time, which is constrained by handling and operational limitations. Consequently, identical targets placed in different core positions can generate substantially different activities.

Optimising Mo-99 output therefore requires locating targets in regions with the most favourable flux and cross-section conditions and scheduling irradiations efficiently. Given that Tc-99m is used in about 85% of diagnostic procedures—around 25 million annually—and that Mo-99 shortages continue to occur [5, 2], even modest improvements in irradiation strategy can significantly enhance global supply reliability and benefit patient care.

1.3. Metaheuristic optimisation

In this study, analytical analyses are performed, but also Evolutionary Algorithms are applied. These metaheuristic, black-box optimisation methods are inspired by biological evolution [6]—with particular emphasis on Genetic Algorithms (GA), which, alongside Differential Evolution, Genetic Programming, and Evolutionary Strategies, represent some of the most established techniques in this domain and have been successfully used in our previous works [7, 8, 9, 10, 11]. In GA the optimised system is encoded as a chromosome, that is, a vector of genes, and a population of such chromosomes is iteratively evolved using three key operators. **Selection with a Fitness Function** imitates natural competition and is typically implemented using roulette, tournament, or ranking strategies [6, 12]. **Crossover** reflects genetic recombination by exchanging gene segments between parents at one or more randomly chosen points [6, 12]. **Mutation** introduces random changes or swaps between genes and expands the exploration of the search space. As heuristic methods, GA cannot guarantee finding the global optimum and may converge asymptotically, become trapped or oscillate around local optima, and in multi-criteria problems

the outcome depends strongly on the formulation of the Fitness Function and the interdependencies among optimised parameters, which often leads to a set of trade-off solutions known as the Pareto Front. In this work, all GA procedures were implemented using the DEAP evolutionary framework [13]. A more detailed description of GA can be found in [6, 7, 8].

Most optimisation studies on isotope production focus on improving core configuration, neutron spectra, or target design rather than optimising the irradiation-loading scheme itself [14, 15]. Efforts typically involve flux enhancement through core reconfiguration or filtering, and accelerator- or geometry-based strategies to increase reaction rates [16, 17]. In research reactors, optimisation has mostly targeted loading-pattern strategies or flux tailoring rather than irradiation scheduling [18]. In this study, our goal is to extend these analyses and attempt to optimise the irradiation strategy, i.e. to identify the optimal way of placing the samples within the core.

2. ANALYTICAL APPROACH TO THE OPTIMISATION PROBLEM

2.1. Definition of the problem

The optimisation of isotope production in a nuclear reactor requires a clear understanding of how irradiation conditions, target utilization, and cycle scheduling influence the buildup of the desired nuclide. Before developing the full optimisation framework, preliminary theoretical analyses were performed to characterize the structure of the problem and to identify key parameters that may influence the optimal irradiation scheme. These analyses focused on evaluating the efficiency of target material utilization under repetitive irradiation cycles, studying the effect of sample shuffling, and assessing the economic implications associated with different irradiation strategies. To quantify the performance of a given irradiation approach, an efficiency measure was introduced, defined as the ratio of the final number of atoms of nuclide B produced after n cycles to the initial number of atoms of the target isotope A :

$$\eta_B(n) = \frac{N_B(n)}{N_A}. \quad (1)$$

To explore this problem, the analysis begins by simplifying the time evolution of nuclide concentrations. In general, the buildup and depletion of isotopes in an irradiated material follow a system of coupled rate equations [19]:

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt} = \sum_j (\lambda_{ji} + \sigma_{ji}\phi(t)) N_j, \quad (2)$$

where N_i is the number of atoms of nuclide $i \in \{1, \dots, I\}$ (I -number of considered isotopes), $\phi(t)$ is the neutron flux ($\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$), λ_{ji} is the decay constant of nuclide j producing i , and σ_{ji} is the reaction cross section producing i . For $j = i$, these terms represent the decay of nuclide i . Solving this full system is computationally intensive, and therefore a simplified case was considered in which nuclide B is produced solely from neutron-induced transmutation of nuclide A , with production governed by cross section $\sigma_{A \rightarrow B}$ and decay of B described by λ_B , without additional reactions or burnup channels. Under these assumptions, the number of atoms of isotope B after an irradiation interval $\Delta\tau$ is given by $N_B(\Delta T, \Delta t) = N_A \alpha_{\Delta T} \beta_{\Delta t}$, where the buildup and decay terms are defined as $\alpha_{\Delta\tau} = \frac{\sigma_{A \rightarrow B} \phi}{\sigma_{A \rightarrow B} \phi + \lambda_B} [1 - e^{-(\sigma_{A \rightarrow B} \phi + \lambda_B) \Delta\tau}]$ and $\beta_{\Delta\tau} = e^{-\lambda_B \Delta\tau}$. The quantity $\alpha_{\Delta\tau}$ represents the effective production efficiency during irradiation, while $\beta_{\Delta\tau}$ describes the survival fraction of isotope B over a cooling period. Using these quantities, the buildup after n repeated irradiation cycles of duration ΔT separated by cooling periods of duration Δt follows the recurrence relation $N_B^{(n)} = N_B^{(n-1)} \beta_{\Delta T + \Delta t} + (N_A - N_B^{(n-1)}) \alpha_{\Delta T}$, with the closed-form solution:

$$N_B^{(n)} = \frac{N_A \alpha_{\Delta T} [1 - (\beta_{\Delta T + \Delta t} - \alpha_{\Delta T})^n]}{1 + \alpha_{\Delta T} - \beta_{\Delta T + \Delta t}}. \quad (3)$$

This expression provides a fast analytical estimate of isotope buildup across multiple cycles and is useful for preliminary exploration of irradiation strategies.

To verify the accuracy of the simplified model, the predictions of Eq. 3 were compared with high-fidelity calculations performed using the Fispack-II inventory code, which solves the full system of rate equations including all major reaction pathways [19]. The benchmark considered production of ^{99}Mo from irradiation of ^{235}U , assuming $N_{U235} = 10^{24}$ atoms and a monoenergetic neutron flux of $\Phi = 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ applied over five cycles of $\Delta T = 5$ days, each followed by a cooling time of $\Delta t = 2$ days, values representative of MARIA reactor operation [1]. The relevant nuclear data include the production cross section $\sigma_{U235 \rightarrow Mo99} = 37 \text{ b}$ [4] and decay constant $\lambda_{Mo99} = 2.9 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$ [20]. The comparison showed good agreement and discrepancies below 5% between the simplified analytical model and the Fispack-II results for the first cycles, confirming that the reduced model is sufficiently accurate for theoretical analyses and for informing the design of the subsequent optimisation framework.

2.2. Optimal number of cycles

Beyond the physical aspects of irradiation planning, economic factors also play a crucial role in determining an optimal isotope-production strategy. The cost of producing nuclide B depends not only on the price of the target material A , but also on the cost associated with occupying space in the reactor core. While the material cost is usually well defined, the operational cost of a research reactor is difficult to quantify due to complex financial structures, fuel expenses, staffing, maintenance, waste management, and long-term decommissioning liabilities [21]. To examine this, it was assumed that the goal is to produce a fixed number N_B^{EXP} of nuclides B , and the required number of target nuclei depends on the number of cycles n through the efficiency $\eta_B(n)$. The cost of production is modeled as the sum of a component proportional to target mass and a component proportional to the number of cycles. The required amount of target material follows directly from the production efficiency, $N_A(n) = N_B^{EXP} / \eta_B(n)$, which links the expected yield to the number of irradiation cycles. The total cost of production is modeled as $C(n) = C_1 n N_A(n) + C_2 N_A(n)$, combining the cycle-dependent irradiation cost and the cost of the target material itself. After scaling by the material cost, the expression simplifies to

$$\hat{C}(n) = \frac{1}{\eta_B(n)} (\zeta n + 1),$$

where $\zeta = C_1/C_2$ represents the ratio of cycle cost to material cost. To compare multi-cycle scenarios with the one-cycle reference case, the relative cost was used:

$$\hat{C}_{rel}(n) = \frac{\hat{C}(n)}{\hat{C}(1)}. \quad (4)$$

This parameterization shows that in our simplified problem whether multi-cycle irradiation is economically beneficial depends entirely on ζ . Figure 2 shows a threshold value, when $\zeta \approx 0.206$ the cost efficiency is the same for irradiation for one and for two cycles. For $\zeta < 0.206$, irradiating for two or more cycles may reduce total cost. When $\zeta > 0.206$, the cost of occupying the reactor core dominates and the economically optimal solution is irradiation for only one cycle (or even a fraction of it).

This simplified analysis demonstrates that the optimal irradiation strategy is strongly dependent on the balance between reactor-operation and material costs, providing a practical criterion for evaluating when extended irradiation is economically justified.

2.2.1. Estimation of ζ value

Estimating the operating cost of a research reactor is highly complex and has been widely studied [22, 23], with uncertainties arising from fuel, maintenance, staffing, waste management, and decommissioning expenses, as well as government-supported financing models often applied to research facilities

Figure 3. optimisation: Irradiation for 4 cycles, 10 samples, GA, $p_c = 0.9$, $p_m = 0.1$, population of 50 specimens.

[24, 22]. In contrast, the cost of target materials is usually better defined, allowing only an approximate determination of the ratio ζ between cycle costs and material costs. The annual operational costs of the MARIA reactor can be roughly estimated as about 3.5 million EUR for maintenance [24], around 0.8 million EUR for fuel replacement based on approximately eight new elements per year [24, 22], and roughly 2.5 million EUR for personnel expenses for a staff of about 100 people [24]. Approximating the usable irradiation volume at about $1.23 \cdot 10^4 \text{ cm}^3$, this corresponds to an irradiation cost of approximately 15.8 EUR/cm^3 per cycle. For Mo-99 production, uranium dioxide enriched to 4% costs about 1283 EUR/cm^3 based on certified reference material pricing [25]. These values yield a ratio $\bar{\zeta} \approx 0.01$, which—despite large uncertainties—remains well below the threshold $\zeta_2 \approx 0.2$ previously identified as the point at which multi-cycle irradiation becomes economically unfavorable. This indicates that, under realistic cost structures, irradiating samples for more than one cycle may still be economically advantageous, although the analysis should be interpreted only as an order-of-magnitude estimate given the substantial simplifications involved.

3. NUMERICAL APPROACH

3.1. Optimisation framework

In addition to the analytical studies presented in the previous sections, a dedicated numerical optimisation framework was developed to perform a full optimisation study. The framework combines a Python-based implementation of a GA using the DEAP library [13], coupled with the Fispact-II inventory code [19] for accurate activation calculations, and supported by neutron-flux and spectral data obtained from Serpent2 Monte Carlo simulations. This integrated approach enables an automated evaluation of thousands of irradiation schemes, allowing the algorithm to explore complex loading, shuffling, and multi-cycle scenarios that are difficult to assess analytically.

In the optimisation process, each chromosome encoded a complete irradiation scheme as a two-dimensional matrix of size $K \times P$, where K is the number of irradiation cycles and P the number of available core positions:

$$[IS]^{K \times P} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{1,1} & \dots & S_{1,P} \\ \vdots & S_{k,p} & \vdots \\ S_{K,1} & \dots & S_{K,P} \end{bmatrix},$$

with each gene $S_{k,p} \in \{1, 2, \dots, K \cdot P\}$. This representation allowed the GA to describe any combination of sample placements, including multi-cycle irradiation, shuffling between positions, or temporary removal from the core. The goal of the optimisation was defined by Eq. 4 (minimization of the relative cost). The analyses were performed for 1 to 4 cycles, 10 positions, and nominal value of $\bar{\zeta} = 0.01$ as well as the sensitivity analyses with $0.1 \cdot \bar{\zeta} = 0.001$ and $10 \cdot \bar{\zeta} = 0.1$.

In this study, a maximum of $K \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ cycles was assumed together with $P = 10$ different irradiation positions characterized by different neutron flux values ranging from 0.93×10^{14} to $1.55 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and by different neutron energy spectra.

3.2. Optimisation

To define the reference case and determine the relative cost, activation calculations were performed for 10 samples (positions) irradiated for one cycle using the Fispact-II code, in order to obtain the value of $\hat{C}(1)$ in Eq. 4. In this reference case, since all samples have the same mass, their arrangement in the core does not affect the overall outcome. The resulting production efficiency of Mo-99 per absorbed U-235 atom was found to be $\eta(1) \approx 5.35 \cdot 10^{-4}$, and this value is used as the reference for evaluating multi-cycle irradiation schemes and their relative production costs.

In the next step, the optimisation algorithm was allowed to explore irradiation schemes involving two, three, and four cycles (the theoretical analyses showed that more would not provide any additional benefit, see Figure 2). Unlike the reference case, the algorithm was free to choose the number of samples used in each scenario, potentially replacing or reintroducing samples between cycles. This enabled the investigation of mixed irradiation strategies, although earlier theoretical considerations suggested that introducing additional samples would not improve efficiency under MARIA reactor conditions. The optimisation was performed using a genetic algorithm with a population of 50 individuals, mutation probability $p_m = 0.1$, and crossover probability $p_c = 0.9$. Figure 3 shows an example of the evolution of the best individual (minimal relative cost) and the average number of samples in the population for irradiation across four cycles. The GA rapidly converges toward solutions with the minimal number of samples, confirming that repeated irradiation of the same material is more efficient than inserting fresh samples. Similar behaviour was observed for cases with irradiation for two and three cycles.

3.3. Results

The optimisation results are summarized in Table I, which compares the achieved production efficiencies and relative production costs for two, three, and four cycles to the one-cycle reference. In all multi-cycle cases, the efficiency η is higher than for the single-cycle scenario, and for sufficiently low ratios of cycle cost to sample cost ($\bar{\zeta}$), multi-cycle irradiation becomes economically favourable. The trends are consistent with theoretical predictions: keeping the same samples in the core across cycles is the dominant contributor to improving efficiency, while introducing new samples increases cost without increasing yield.

Table I. Summary of optimised irradiation schemes for 4-, 3-, and 2-cycle scenarios compared with the 1-cycle reference.

Case	η	$\hat{C}_{rel}[\%]$		
		$\bar{\zeta} = 0.001$	$\bar{\zeta} = 0.01$	$\bar{\zeta} = 0.1$
4-cycles	6.16×10^{-4}	87.0	89.3	110.4
3-cycles	6.25×10^{-4}	85.8	87.3	101.1
2-cycles	6.20×10^{-4}	86.4	87.1	94.1
1-cycle	5.35×10^{-4}	100.0	100.0	100.0

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a combined analytical and numerical framework for optimising radioisotope production in the MARIA reactor, with a focus on improving the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of multi-cycle irradiation strategies for ^{99}Mo . Analytical studies showed that repeated irradiation of the same target material may improve utilization efficiency, while the economic benefit of multi-cycle schemes depends primarily on the ratio ζ between reactor-operation cost and target-material cost.

A full optimisation study using a Genetic Algorithm coupled with Fispect-II confirmed the analytical findings. The GA consistently converged toward solutions that reuse the same samples across cycles, and shuffling the samples provides only a smaller gain. The improvement originates predominantly from repeated irradiation rather than spatial rearrangement of samples, nevertheless, the analyses showed that the optimal irradiation strategy can reduce the cost by up to 14%.

Overall, the results demonstrate that multi-cycle irradiation of a fixed set of targets represents the most efficient and cost-effective strategy for Mo-99 production under MARIA reactor conditions. The developed optimisation framework is general and can be directly applied to other radionuclides, reactor configurations, or target designs, offering a systematic tool for enhancing isotope-production performance.

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